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● Revision of the genus *Metapone* Forel, 1911 from China (Hymenoptera: Formicidae)

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Abstract: This revision of the Chinese species of *Metapone* included a known species, *M. sauteri* Forel, 1912, as well as the descriptions of two new species: *M. nigrolucidus* sp. nov. and *M. shanyii* sp. nov. Additionally, high-resolution color images of each species were provided, along with a key to the Chinese species of *Metapone* genus based on queen caste.

Keywords: Crematogastrini, key, Myrmicinae, termite predators

● 中国后蚁属分类修订（膜翅目：蚁科）

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摘要: 本文对中国蚁科后蚁属共 3 种蚂蚁进行了分类修订, 包括一个已知种——邵氏后蚁 *M. sauteri* Forel, 1912, 并描述了 2 个新种, 即亮黑后蚁 *M. nigrolucidus* sp. nov. 与善义后蚁 *M. shanyii* sp. nov.。此外, 本文还提供了中国后蚁属每个种高清彩图, 以及编写了中国后蚁属的分种检索表。

关键词: 举腹蚁族, 检索表, 切叶蚁亚科, 白蚁捕食者

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Introduction

The genus *Metapone* is one of the most unusual and mysterious ants in the Old World. It was established by Forel (1911) based on a series of workers, larvae, and reproductive pupae of *Metapone greeni* Forel collected from Sri Lanka. Bolton (2003) regarded it as the sole genus within the tribe Metaponini. However, recent molecular data confirm *Metapone* as a member of the tribe Crematogastrini (Ward *et al.* 2015). This genus currently comprises 31 known species, primarily distributed in the Oriental, Australian, and Malagasy Regions. Almost half of these species (14/31) have been established based on single queens (13/31) or males (1/31) collected during nuptial flights. Taylor & Alpert (2016) conducted a global taxonomic revision of all species within this genus, reviewing 28 species, including the descriptions of 12 new species. This laid a solid foundation for subsequent taxonomic studies of this genus. Two years later, Taylor (2018) described three new species collected from New Caledonia and Vanuatu, while Wang *et al.* (2019) described a new species collected from Singapore. Since then, no new species of this genus have been reported. The mystery surrounding this genus stems from its unique biological habit of symbiosis with termites. Most of the collected workers are associated with termites, and all species of this genus have stout legs adapted for living within termite galleries, functioning as termite predators (Forel 1911; Wheeler 1919, 1936; Taylor 1991; Eguchi 1998). Hölldobler & Leibig *et al.* (2002) and Hölldobler & Oldham *et al.* (2002) further emphasize the role of *Metapone* species as specialized termite predators in symbiotic relationships.

Currently, the genus *Metapone* is highly diverse in the entire Oriental Region, with a total of 11 species. However, there is only one recorded species in China, namely *Metapone sauteri* Forel, 1912, which is exclusively found in Taiwan Province. The authors of this paper obtained materials from Yunnan, China, and after identification, confirmed two new species, namely *M. nigrolucidus* **sp. nov.** and *M. shanyii* **sp. nov.** Consequently, the known species count of this genus within China has increased from the original one to three. This paper revises these three known species, providing high-resolution color images, morphological identification characteristics, and a key for distinguishing female castes of different species.

Material and methods

The specimens were manually collected from decayed wood on the forest floor in a pristine forest and have been archived in the following repositories: (1) GXNU (Insect Collection, Guangxi Normal University, Guilin, Guangxi, China); (2) SWFU (Insect Collection, Southwest Forestry University, Kunming, Yunnan, China). Examination of the specimens was carried out using a Leica M205A stereomicroscope. High-quality multi-focused montage images were produced using the KEYENCE (VHX-6000) digital imaging system. Measurements are presented in millimeters. The measurements and indices are delineated as follows: **CI**—Cephalic Index = $HW \times 100 / HL$; **DPI**—Dorsal Petiole Index = $DPW \times 100 / PL$; **DPW**—Dorsal Petiole Width, maximum width of petiole in dorsal view; **ED**—Eye Diameter, maximum diameter of eye; **HL**—Head Length, straight-line length of head in full-face view, measured from midpoint of anterior clypeal margin to midpoint of posterior margin, or terminal horizontal line in some species with a concave posterior margin; **HW**—Head Width, maximum width of head in full-face view, excluding eyes; **LPI**—Lateral Petiole Index = $PH \times 100 / PL$; **MSL**—Mesosoma Length, diagonal length of mesosoma in lateral view, measured from point at which pronotum meets cervical shield to posterior basal angle of metapleuron; **PH**—Petiole Height, height of petiole measured in lateral view from apex of ventral (subpetiolar) process vertically to a line intersecting dorsal most point of node; **PL**—Petiole Length, length of petiole measured in lateral view from anterior process to posterior most point of tergite, where it surrounds gastral articulation; **PW**—Pronotal Width, maximum width of pronotum measured in dorsal view; **SI**—Scape Index = $SL \times 100 / HW$; **SL**—Scape Length, straight-line length of antennal scape, excluding basal constriction or neck; **TL**—Total Length, total outstretched length of individual, from mandibular (occlusion) apex to gastral apex (not including the sting).

Taxonomy

Key to known Chinese species of *Metapone* based on queen castes

- 1 Dorsal surface smooth and shining.....*M. nigrolucidus* **sp. nov.**
- Dorsal surface of head densely, finely, longitudinally striate.....2
- 2 In full-face view, lateral margins of protruding part of clypeus shallow curved concave. Surface of clypeus smooth and shining, or very slight and longitudinal densely striate. In lateral view, spiracle of propodeum located above midline, closer to dorsal face; subpetiolar lamella subtrapezoidal...*Metapone sauteri* Forel, 1912
- In full-face view, lateral margins of protruding part of clypeus parallel. Surface of clypeus longitudinal oblique striate densely. In lateral view, spiracle of propodeum located on lateral midsection; Subpetiolar lamella forming hook pointing backwards.....*M. shanyii* **sp. nov.**

Metapone nigrolucidus **sp. nov.** 亮黑后蚁

<https://zoobank.org/D07B3FC9-0D92-4503-847A-B2F8B16AE3E5>

Fig. 1

Type material. Holotype alate queen, Jinghong City, Xishuangbanna Dai Autonomous Prefecture, Yunnan Province, China, 21.471668°N, 100.604934°E, 10.XII.2023, Ying-Ke Yan leg., No. GXNU 238702. (Holotype in GXNU).

Etymology. The defining characteristics of this species are its black body and shimmering surface. Inspired by these traits, we named it “nigrolucidus”, a compound Latin term derived from the roots “niger” (black) and “lucidus” (shiny).

Measurements (alate queen). TL 7.86, HL 1.51, HW 1.38, CI 91, SL 0.56, SI 41, ED 0.56, PW 1.27, MSL 2.55, PL 0.61, PH 0.40, DPW 0.79 (n = 1).

Diagnosis (alate queen). Body black, with head and dorsum of mesosoma smooth and shining, dorsum of petiole as long as it’s wide.

Description (alate queen). In full-face view, head trapezoidal, narrow anteriorly, posterior margin straight, and posterolateral corners of head rounded. Mandibles strap-shaped, with five teeth along masticatory margin, gradually decreasing in size from apex to base. Clypeus frontal triangle, and anterior margin of head completely fused, clypeus projecting trapezoidally, with anterior margin slightly convex, and anterior corners bluntly angled. Antennae completely covered by frontal lobes, with a deep antennal scrobe extending posterolaterally, almost to posterior margin of eyes, antennal groove accommodative to entire antennal scape. Antennae 11 segments, with scape segments being club-shaped, and flagellar segments gradually increasing in size towards apex, with terminal three segments compressed laterally. Eyes well-developed, with a diameter exceeding 1/4 of length of lateral margins of head, situated posterior to midline of head and slightly below. Three prominent ocelli situated at vertex.

In lateral view, ventral margin of head convex, with ridges visible on poster-lower margin of head. Mesosoma stout and short, convex dorsally. Anterodorsal corners of pronotum obtuse, with posterior margin bluntly rounded, fitting into upper lateral portion of mesonotum. Mesopleural dorsum slightly convex, with a distinct shallow groove separating anepisternum and katepisternum. Metapleuron cuneiform. Propodeal dorsum slightly convex, gradually decreasing posteriorly, with a convex declivity, and junction between dorsum and declivity forms a bluntly rounded transition. Petiole concave both anteriorly and posteriorly, with anterodorsal corners forming a sharp angle and posterior dorsal angle extending backward into a blunt spine-like projection; Subpetiolar process triangular. Anterior margin of postpetiole slightly convex, while posterior margin concave, with a straight dorsal margin. Tergites of postpetiole concave in middle, with subpostpetiolar process forming a bluntly rounded projection. Anterior margin of gaster closely and broadly attached to posterior margin of postpetiole, with first segment comprising approximately half length of entire gaster.

FIGURE 1. *Metapone nigrolucidus* sp. nov., alate queen: **A** head in full-face view **B** body in dorsal view **C** body in lateral view. Scale = 0.5 mm.

In dorsal view, pronotum crescent-shaped, with a convex anterior margin, anterolateral corners resembling shoulder-like angles, and posterior margin with a curved depression. Anterior margin of mesoscutum rounded, while posterior margin convex, but not smoothly rounded. Transscutal line forms a shallow arc-shaped depression, and anterior margin of mesoscutellum bearing a discontinuous arcuate stripe. Metanotum transversely narrow rectangular, and dorsum of propodeum rectangular, concave posteriorly, with sharp posterolateral corners. Petiole concave anteriorly, with rounded anterolateral corners, slightly convex lateral margins, and divergent posteriorly; posterior margin curvedly depressed, with posterior corners projecting in a tooth-like manner. Postpetiole horizontally elliptical.

Head, mesosoma, petiole, postpetiole, and gaster smooth and shining, except for longitudinal striations present on antennal scrobes, lateral sides of pronotum, lower half of lateral sides of propodeum, and lower half of lateral sides of petiole. Body surface scattered with suberect long strong hairs and short fine suberect hairs. Head black, mandibles and antennae reddish-brown. Mesosoma black, coxae black with reddish-brown apices, femora and first tarsi reddish-brown, remaining tarsi yellowish-brown. Petiole and postpetiole black, gaster predominantly black

with segments ending and lateral margins of each tergite reddish-brown.

Habitat. This new species is captured using light traps, but detailed biological information is currently unavailable.

Remarks. This new species closely resembles *Metapone bakeri* Wheeler, 1916, in morphology, as both exhibit robust, shiny black bodies. However, they can be easily distinguished: in this new species, the dorsal surface of the clypeus is smooth and lacks a median ridge, whereas in *M. bakeri* with a median ridge. In this new species, distinct longitudinal striations are present below the antennal scrobes and on the lateral sides of the pronotum, whereas in *M. bakeri*, these areas are smooth and shining. Furthermore, in dorsal view, the petiole width of this new species is notably greater than its length, whereas in *M. bakeri*, the length equal to width. Additionally, in lateral view, the dorsal surface of the postpetiole in this new species is straight, whereas in *M. bakeri*, it appears slightly convex.

Metapone sauteri Forel, 1912 邵氏后蚁

Fig. 2

Metapone sauteri Forel, 1912: 763 China (Taiwan).

Type material: Unexamined. But two syntype images of queen (CASENT0907445 & FOCOL0372, imaged by Will Ericson and Christiana Klingenberg respectively) were reviewed from <https://www.antweb.org>.

Diagnosis (queen). Head and mesosoma blackish-brown, while the gaster reddish-brown. Clypeus smooth and shining. In full-face view, the posterior margin of head concave; the anterior part of the clypeus wider than the middle part. In lateral view, the spiracle of the propodeum located above the midline; the subpetiolar process of the petiole rectangular.

Metapone shanyii sp. nov. 善义后蚁

<https://zoobank.org/2BB5863B-B10E-4915-B18C-113EFBB8F1CA>

Figs 3, 4

Type material. Holotype worker, Jinghong City, Xishuangbanna Dai Autonomous Prefecture, Yunnan Province, China, 21.470944°N, 100.610925°E, 27.V.2023, Ying-Ke Yan leg., No. GXNU 238703. **Paratypes:** two queens, same colony as the holotype. (Holotype and one paratype queen in GXNU; one paratype queen in SWFU).

Etymology. This new species is named “Shanyi” in honor of the late Chinese ant taxonomist, Mr. Shan-Yi Zhou, to commemorate his exceptional contributions to studying ant taxonomy in China.

Measurements (worker). TL 7.60, HL 1.38, HW 1.06, CI 77, SL 0.41, SI 39, ED 0.13, PW 0.75, MSL 2.08, PL 0.56, PH 0.47, DPW 0.46.

Measurements (alate queen). TL 9.01–9.48, HL 1.64–1.72, HW 1.08–1.10, CI 63–66, SL 0.52–0.53, SI 48, ED 0.50–0.51, PW 1.05–1.07, MSL 2.99–3.01, PL 0.83–0.88, PH 0.54–0.58, DPW 0.51–0.55 (n = 2).

Diagnosis (worker). Head and mesosoma bear longitudinal striations. Anterior part of clypeus protrudes in a rectangular shape, and subpetiolar process exhibits a distinct hook-like projection.

Description (worker). In full-face view, head rectangular, anterolateral margin before eyes slightly constricted, posterior margin straight, and posterolateral corners rounded. Mandibles subtriangular, with 7–8 prominent teeth along masticatory margin. Anterior part of clypeus rectangularly protruding, with a straight anterior margin. Antennal scrobes concave, capable of accommodating entire scape of antennae. Eyes flat, not prominently protruding, with maximum diameter approximately equal to widest part of scape of antennae.

FIGURE 2. *Metapone sauteri* Forel, 1912, syntype queen (from <https://www.antweb.org/>, FOCOL0372, imaged by Christiana Klingenberg): **A** head in full-face view **B** body in dorsal view **C** body in lateral view.

In lateral view, dorsal surface of mesosoma flat, with slight traces of a metanotal groove. Dorsum of propodeum decreased on posterior one-third, meeting with declivity into a bluntly rounded corner; propodeal lobes rounded. Anterior margin of petiole concave, with a narrow rounded anterodorsal corner, a convex dorsal surface, and a blunt tooth-like projection on posterodorsal corner. Subpetiolar process as a backward-facing hook, with triangular teeth on posteroventral part. Anterior and dorsal margin of postpetiole convex, anterodorsal corner rounded, while ventral margin of postpetiole concave, with a robust triangular projection on anteroventral corner. In dorsal view, anterior margin of mesosoma convex, with a pair of prominent shoulders, and nearly straight lateral margins converging posteriorly, posterior margin concave and posterolateral corners angled; Anterior mesonotal suture exhibiting a

slightly broad V-shaped impression, and metanotal groove evident. Petiole longer than it's width, narrower anteriorly, with a concave posterior margin and tooth-like projections on posterolateral corners. Postpetiole appears elliptical, with a slightly concave posterior margin in middle.

Clypeus, head, and mandibles with longitudinal striations. Dorsal surface of mesosoma with longitudinal striations, except for a narrow, smooth and shining area in middle portion of propodeum. lateral sides of mesosoma with weak transverse wrinkles. Lower part of sides of petiole with weak wrinkles, lateral part of dorsum of petiole shallow longitudinal striations. Postpetiole and gaster smooth and shiny, except for scattered piligerous punctures. Erect hairs distributed across body, while decumbent pubescence more abundant on gaster. Head black, dorsal surface of pronotum blackish-brown, and lateral sides of mesosoma, petiole, and postpetiole reddish-brown, while legs and gaster yellowish-brown.

FIGURE 3. *Metapone shanyii* sp. nov., holotype worker: **A** head in full-face view **B** body in dorsal view **C** body in lateral view. Scale = 0.5 mm.

Description (alate queen). The morphological characteristics of alate queen similar to those of worker, except for presence of three ocelli at vertex of head, more prominent longitudinal striations on body surface, and distinctly hooked subpetiolar process.

Habitat. This species primarily inhabits the decaying wood on both sides of mountain valley streams in tropical seasonal rainforests, nesting near the center of the decaying wood, and preying on species of the genus *Glyptotermes* (Blattodea: Kalotermitidae) found within the same decaying wood.

FIGURE 4. *Metapone shanyii* sp. nov., paratype queens: **A, D** heads in full-face view **B, E** bodies in dorsal view **C, F** bodies in lateral view. Scale = 0.5 mm.

Remarks. The new species resembles *M. sauteri* Forel, 1912, in body sizes and longitudinal striations on the mesosoma. The former, however, can be distinguished morphologically from the latter as follows: this new species is covered with rich longitudinal striations on dorsal surface of the clypeus, contrasting with smooth and shining in *M. sauteri*; the straight posterior margin of the head in this new species, compared to concave posterior margin of *M. sauteri*; the protruding anterior part of the clypeus in this new species is rectangular, while in *M. sauteri* is trapezoidal; the distinctly hook-shaped projection of subpetiolar process of this new species, where the height and length are nearly equal, whereas in *M. sauteri*, it tends to be more trapezoidal, with length significantly exceeding height.

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Additional information

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